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Effect of Nutrient Solution Exposure Interval to Magnetic Field on the Growth and Yield of Hydroponically Grown Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*)

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Abstract

Objectives: This study explored the effect of the varying nutrient solution exposure intervals to a magnetic field on the growth and yield parameters for lettuce grown in a soilless cultivation system. **Method:** The study utilized a two-factor factorial experiment arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The two factors were the number of magnets (Factor A) and nutrient solution exposure intervals (Factor B) to magnetic field. Statistical significance was determined through ANOVA and Tukey's HSD. **Findings:** Except for root fresh weight, all growth and yield parameters were significantly influenced by the two factors considered in the study. In addition, annual electrical energy consumption increased by 180-200% when shifting from every-three-day to daily exposure, alongside the increase in frequency of exposure (shorter intervals). However, this was accompanied by a 23.76% improvement in lettuce leaf fresh weight which could justify additional energy expenditure. In conclusion, increasing the number of magnets and increasing frequency of exposure (shorter intervals) resulted in improved lettuce growth and yield performance. **Novelty:** This study provides novel data on the interaction between magnetization frequency and energy efficiency. The results could be used as a framework for the optimization of the combination of MWT and hydroponics system.

Keywords: Magnetic Water Treatment; Lettuce; Hydroponics; Exposure Interval; Nutrient Solution

1 Introduction

Global population is projected to reach 9.8 billion by 2050⁽¹⁾, which potentially exacerbates current global food security challenges including a 50-70% increase in food demand^{(2), (3)}. The situation is further aggravated by declining areas of arable land due to rapid land conversion and urbanization⁽⁴⁾ and degrading soil quality due to erosion, pollution, and seawater intrusion, rendering it unsuitable for agriculture⁽⁵⁾. These conditions necessitate alternative approaches for agricultural intensification.

In recent years, hydroponics has emerged as a viable cultivation system, offering higher yield compared to traditional cultivation systems. As mentioned by several researchers, hydroponics system provided several advantages which includes reduction of arable land reliance, increased water use efficiency, and enhanced crop growth and yield parameters^{(6), (7)}. However, this cultivation system faces nutrient solution management related challenges especially nutrient depletion, water quality deterioration, and potential accumulation of particulate matters which could lead to nutrient imbalances and inhibit root uptake^{(8), (9)}.

On the other hand, magnetic water treatment (MWT) provides further enhancement on crop productivity which is done by passing nutrient solution (or water) through a magnetic field, a process called magnetization. Magnetization offers beneficial modification on the water quality including alterations in hydrogen bonding, viscosity, and surface tension, as well as reduction on water cluster size, leading to an overall enhancement on water absorption and nutrient transport in plants^{(10), (11)}. In addition, the application of magnetic field affects plant metabolism by stimulating enzyme activity and protein synthesis during early seedling development and by enhancing water and nutrient uptake in later stages of development^{(12), (13), (14)}.

Recent studies conducted have demonstrated that magnetic field application enhanced growth and yield of hydroponic lettuce^{(15), (16)}, and hydroponic pechay⁽¹⁷⁾. In addition, lettuce grown in drip fertigation systems⁽¹⁸⁾ and tomato grown in aquaponic systems⁽¹⁹⁾ showed improvements in similar aspects. Furthermore, new related advancements in magnetic water technology reported an enhancement in nutrient recovery and water efficiency in hydroponic systems with a 15% increase in nutrient retention efficiency and 20% reductions in operational costs⁽²⁰⁾.

These studies have shown remarkable potential for the application of MWT in hydroponics system; however, a critical knowledge gap remains on the aspect of operational parameters influencing technical efficacy. Specifically, the duration and exposure interval of nutrient solutions to magnetic field have received limited systematic investigation both on its effect on plants response and system's energy consumption. As suggested by Surendran et al.⁽²¹⁾, the effect of magnetization of water and nutrient solution may persist for 24–48 hours which implies that continuous recirculation might be unnecessary, subsequently reducing energy consumption while maintaining or enhancing crop growth and yield. However, no studies have systematically examined how varying exposure intervals interact with magnetic field strength to influence plant growth parameters, yield performance, and energy efficiency in integrated hydroponic and MWT systems.

This study addresses this gap by investigating the effects of nutrient solution exposure interval to magnetic fields on lettuce growth and yield in hydroponic culture. The findings provide novel data on the interaction between magnetization frequency and energy efficiency, offering a framework for optimizing the combination of MWT and hydroponics for both enhanced crop productivity and operational energy considerations.

2 Methodology

The study followed these general procedures.

2.1 Preparation and Establishment of Experimental Area

The experimental area was established at the College of Engineering, Cagayan State University – Sanchez Mira Campus at a location with at least five (5) hours of sunlight exposure daily. The hydroponic setups were constructed and placed in a 6-m x 6-m greenhouse.

Hydroponic setups were positioned and spaced to minimize and limit the interference between magnets. They were spaced at 60-cm distance between treatments and 120-cm distance between blocks. A UV film was used to provide shading and to protect the plants from direct sunlight, and to prevent rainwater from being mixed with the nutrient solution.

2.2 Preparation and Construction of the Hydroponic Setup

The hydroponic setup (Figure 1) was constructed and assembled with the following components: (a) pipe system, (b) frame system, (c) nutrient solution recirculating device (pump), (d) growing chamber and (e) nutrient reservoir.

The frame system (b) was constructed using 5 cm x 5 cm (2 in x 2 in) wood which holds the other components of the setup. The growing chamber (d) and the nutrient reservoir (e) were made of 200-L drum cut longitudinally in half. The upper part serves as the growing chamber while the lower part serves as the nutrient reservoir. Also, the growing chamber was equipped with a cover which held the Styrofoam cups and the seedling plugs.

Through the submersible pump (c), recirculation of the nutrient solution was obtained. Other components include the pipe system, connected to the pump, which serves as a channel for the nutrient solution to flow from the nutrient reservoir (e) to the growing chamber (d). Furthermore, the setup has a total dimension of 1.2 m x 0.85 m x 1.5 m (L x W x H).

Fig 1. The hydroponic setup used in the study

2.3 Preparation of Seedlings and Transplanting

The preparation of seedlings involved the preparation of soil media with a 100% cocopeat on a seedling tray followed by sowing of seeds. Twenty-one days after sowing, the seedlings were transplanted and were placed on a seedling sponge that held the seedlings and eventually were placed on a Styrofoam cup. The cups were then placed in the cover of growing chamber provided with holes. A total of 414 seedlings (cups) were placed in the 18 hydroponic setups.

2.4 Magnetization Process

Neodymium permanent magnets (N52 Grade, 2.0 cm x 1 cm x 0.5 cm) were used to facilitate the magnetization process. The strengths of the magnets were not measured in this study; however, the number of magnets was assumed to be proportional to magnetic field strength. As presented in Figure 2, the magnets were placed outside the pipes and were arranged in alternating polarity (e.g., north-south). The placement of the magnets in the hydroponics setup was shown in Figure 1. With the aid of the submersible pump, which recirculates the nutrient solution through the piping system and the chambers, magnetization was achieved.

2.5 Statistical Treatments and Data Gathering

The study utilized a two-factor factorial experiment arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The two factors were the number of magnets (Factor A: Two Levels; A1 = No Magnet, A2 = 12 Magnets) and nutrient solution exposure intervals (Factor B: Three Levels; B1 = everyday, B2 = every two days; B3 = every three days) to magnetic field. These form a total of six treatment combinations which were then replicated three times resulting in a total number of eighteen hydroponic setups.

The growth and yield parameters gathered include plant height (cm), number of leaves per plant, root length (cm), leaf area (cm²), leaf fresh weight (g), root fresh weight (g), total fresh weight (g), and dry weight (g). The plant height and number of leaves were measured weekly from transplanting to the time of harvest (28 Days After Transplanting (DAT)), and the other parameters were all determined at harvest. In each parameter, 10 randomly selected representative samples per setup were considered. The response parameters were analyzed using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). On the other hand, Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) was used to further compare treatments means.

Fig 2. Arrangement of permanent magnet outside the pipe

2.6 Electrical Energy Consumption

The total annual electrical energy consumption of a single hydroponic setup was determined based on power rating of the pump, number of hours of operation, and total number of cycles in a year. The formula used was shown in equation below.

$$E_{\text{Annual}} = (P \times N_{\text{Hours}} \times N_{\text{Days}} \times N_{\text{Cycles}}) / 1000 \quad (1)$$

where:

E_{Annual} = annual energy consumption, kWh

P = power rating of the pump, W

N_{Hours} = number of hours of operation per day, h/day

N_{Days} = pump duration of operation per cycle, days per cycle

N_{Cycles} = number of cycles per year

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Growth Performance of Lettuce

The lettuce growth performances on plant height (cm), number of leaves, root length (cm), and leaf area (cm^2) at harvest (28 DAT) as influenced by the number of magnets (Factor A) and nutrient solution exposure intervals (Factor B) are presented in Table 1. Based on the result, it can be noted that the effect of 12 magnets (A2) and daily exposure interval (B1) resulted in higher plants, longer roots, a greater number of leaves, and larger leaf areas. This pattern consistently observed across these growth parameters suggests that increasing the number of magnets (or magnetic field strength) and shortening the exposure interval resulted in a positive growth response.

Based on the ANOVA result, the main effects of factors A and B significantly influenced the plant height ($p < 0.01$), root length ($p < 0.01$), number of leaves ($p < 0.05$), and leaf area ($p < 0.05$). This result revealed that both factors contribute to the enhancement of vegetative development in lettuce for these parameters, independently. Conversely, the interaction effect only showed significant influence on the leaf area ($p < 0.05$) which could imply that the combined effect of the two factors is not merely an additive but shows a significant interdependence between the two factors. This interaction effect indicates that increasing the number of magnets only results in an absolute reduction in leaf area if daily exposure interval is not maintained. Additionally, blocks showed significant influence on plant height, number of leaves, and root length, implying that the use of blockings through RCBD on the experiment is effective. This validates that the inherent environmental gradients which potentially include variations in light intensity or temperature within the greenhouse were successfully accounted for in the experimental design. If partitioning had not been done, this could have inflated the error potentially reducing the statistical power to detect treatment differences.

Moreover, a significant increase of 8.54% in plant height, 16.15% in root length, 5.48% in number of leaves, and 8.28% in leaf area was noted when nutrient solutions were exposed to a magnetic field compared to the non-magnetized control. This increase in growth performance can be attributed to the ability of magnetic fields to enhance the mobility of water and

Table 1. Main effects of Number of Magnets (Factor A) and Nutrient Solution Exposure Interval (Factor B) on the growth performance of Lettuce using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test

Factors	Mean \pm SD	% Change	p-values [HSD (0.05)]		
			Factor	A x B	Block
Plant Height (cm) Grand Mean = 26.61 \pm 2.12 CV = 4.13 %					
A1	25.52 \pm 1.18 ^a	-	0.0018		
A2	27.70 \pm 2.34 ^b	+8.54%	[1.63]		
B1	27.91 \pm 2.51 ^a			(0.6257)	0.0032
B2	26.19 \pm 1.49 ^{ab}	-6.16%	0.0151		
B3	25.74 \pm 1.89 ^b	-7.78%	[2.47]		
Root Length (cm) Grand Mean = 44.69 \pm 6.07 CV = 5.64 %					
A1	41.34 \pm 3.77 ^a		0.0002		
A2	48.03 \pm 6.23 ^b	+16.15%	[3.74]		
B1	49.35 \pm 7.03 ^a			(0.0898)	0.0122
B2	44.00 \pm 3.69 ^b	-10.82%	0.0005		
B3	40.70 \pm 4.02 ^b	-17.55%	[5.64]		
Number of Leaves Grand Mean = 12.56 \pm 1.10 CV = 4.97 %					
A1	12.22 \pm 1.09 ^a	-	0.0467		
A2	12.89 \pm 1.05 ^b	+5.48%	[0.93]		
B1	13.17 \pm 0.75 ^a			(0.6629)	0.0017
B2	12.50 \pm 1.05 ^a	-5.09%	0.0271		
B3	12.00 \pm 1.26 ^b	-8.88%	[1.40]		
Leaf Area (cm²) Grand Mean = 167.31 \pm 14.57 CV = 5.36 %					
A1	160.66 \pm 14.76 ^a	-	0.0103		
A2	173.97 \pm 11.56 ^b	+8.28%	[13.31]		
B1	176.19 \pm 11.23 ^a			0.0150 [35.92]	(0.2672)
B2	163.05 \pm 7.15 ^b	-7.46%	0.0421		
B3	162.70 \pm 20.06 ^b	-7.66%	[20.07]		

Note: a) Means of the same superscript are statistically the same. b) Bold face indicates significance at $p < 0.05$; not significant values are shown in parentheses. c) % Change is calculated relative to the first treatment level within each factor.

nutrients^{(21), (22)} facilitating their easy absorption^{(13), (14)}, thereby improving nutrient uptake efficiency. These observations can be further explained by recent evidence on the effect of magnetic fields at the molecular level. Zhou et al.⁽²³⁾ reported that plants' exposure to static magnetic fields promotes cell elongation and improves enzyme activity confirming the increase in growth parameters observed in this study. The increase in growth parameters conforms with the results of several studies on hydroponic lettuce^{(15), (16)}, hydroponic pechay⁽¹⁷⁾, and other crop species⁽¹⁴⁾.

The improvement observed in this study, particularly on root length (16.15%), is slightly higher than the range typically reported by Agcaoili⁽¹⁵⁾ and Adorio et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ which utilized continuous magnetic exposure. More importantly, extending the exposure interval to every two or three days significantly reduced root length (by 10.82% and 17.55%, respectively), confirming that the biological benefits of magnetization decay rapidly and require frequent (daily) renewal which is a key novel finding of this work. In addition, the findings of this study demonstrate that the root system responded more dramatically than previously recognized⁽¹⁴⁾ with implications for improving nutrient uptake efficiency in plants.

Furthermore, exposing the nutrient solution to magnetic fields at longer intervals (two-day and three-day interval) significantly reduced growth performance compared to daily exposure. For plant height, decreases of 6.16% and 7.78% were observed; for root length, decreases of 10.82% and 17.55% were recorded; for number of leaves, decreases of 5.09% and 8.88% were noted; and for leaf area, reductions of 7.46% and 7.66% were measured for every-two-day and every-three-day intervals, respectively. Based on this result, an inverse relationship between nutrient solution exposure interval and growth parameters is established.

This finding suggests that biological benefits of magnetization for plant growth diminish more rapidly than its physical effect on water. In addition, nutrient solutions require continuous or near-continuous exposure to magnetic field in order to

affect significant growth in plants. Hafeez et al.⁽²⁴⁾ noted that inconsistent outcomes in magnetic field research often relate to exposure timing parameters, and our results confirm that exposure interval is a critical factor determining treatment efficacy. This observation agrees with the claims of several studies regarding the importance of exposure frequency in maximizing magnetic field benefits⁽²⁴⁾.

This interval-dependent response contrasts with the assumption that magnetization effects persist uniformly for 24-48 hours⁽²¹⁾. The study's results indicate that while water properties may retain physical changes, the biological benefits for plant growth decay more rapidly requiring daily exposure to sustain maximum growth responses. This finding refines our understanding of MWT applications in recirculating systems and provides empirical data on optimal exposure intervals for hydroponic lettuce production.

3.2 Yield Performance of Lettuce

The lettuce yield performances on leaf fresh weight (g), root fresh weight (g), total fresh weight (g), and dry weight (g) as influenced by the number of magnets (Factor A) and nutrient solution exposure intervals (Factor B) are presented in Table 2. Based on the result, the influence of 12 magnets (A2) and daily exposure interval (B1) resulted in the heaviest weight across all weight parameters. This observation on yields parameters aligns with the observation in growth parameters, which indicates that the enhancement on growth parameters (vegetative development) directly translates into biomass accumulation.

Statistical analysis, however, revealed that leaf fresh weight, total fresh weight, and dry weight were significantly influenced ($p < 0.01$) by the main effects of factors A and B, and the root fresh weight was not significantly affected ($p > 0.05$). These significant main effects on above-ground biomass parameters indicate that the two factors independently contribute to an increase in marketable yield for hydroponic lettuce. Furthermore, while root length showed enhancement, the lack of significance in root fresh weight suggests that the magnetic field promotes longitudinal root elongation rather than lateral thickening, indicating that the roots prioritize nutrient seeking rather than biomass accumulation. Conversely, the interaction effects showed no significance across all the yield parameters. This indicates that the effect of number of magnets on these yield parameters does not vary regardless of nutrient solution exposure interval and vice versa. Despite significant interaction effects observed for leaf area, its absence in yield parameters indicates that the effect of the two factors manifests primarily during the vegetative growth (leaf area development) rather than during the final biomass accumulation phase. Additionally, blocks showed a significant effect throughout the yield parameters further confirming the efficacy of the blocking technique in controlling environmental gradients. The consistent results on growth and yield stages validate the initial observations and reinforces the structural integrity of the experimental design.

Moreover, a significant increase of 23.76% in leaf fresh weight, 19.90% in total fresh weight, and 20.36% in dry weight was observed when nutrient solutions were exposed to magnetic field compared to the non-magnetized control. This substantial gain in yield parameters directly corroborates the previously noted increase in root length (16.15%). The enhancement of above-ground biomass, with concurrent root elongation, may reflect that the exposure of nutrient solutions to magnetic field accelerates crop productivity. This further explains the simultaneous optimization of nutrient acquisition at the root zone and nutrient utilization within the plant tissues. These results are consistent with the observations and claims of several research studies on hydroponic lettuce⁽¹⁵⁾,⁽¹⁶⁾, hydroponic pechay⁽¹⁷⁾, and other crop species⁽¹⁴⁾.

The magnitude of yield improvement observed in this study, particularly the 23.76% increase in leaf fresh weight with daily nutrient solution exposure interval, agrees with previous reports. Despite differences in baseline condition, the observed increase in leaf fresh weight agrees with Okasha et al.⁽²⁵⁾ which reported a 109-112% increase in fresh weight of hydroponic lettuce under magnetically treated saline water. In contrast, the current study used optimal nutrient solutions, and the reported increase represents an enhancement above an optimal growing condition. While recent studies demonstrated that higher magnetic intensities produce correspondingly greater yield improvements⁽²⁶⁾, this study contributes another dimension particularly on the nutrient solution exposure interval which independently influenced yield even at constant magnetic field strength.

While the root fresh weight was not significantly affected by the magnetic field, even with a notable effect on root length, this result still conforms with previous research studies. The magnetic field triggers a certain hormone responsible for cell elongation (lengthening of roots) before the plant converts it to biomass⁽²⁷⁾,⁽²⁸⁾. Hence, the divergent effect between root length and root fresh weight. This differential response can now be understood through recent molecular evidence although from a different crop species. In the study conducted by Zhou et al.⁽²³⁾ on Arabidopsis, it demonstrated that static magnetic fields upregulate auxin synthesis and signal transduction genes. This effect promoted cell elongation rather than biomass accumulation. This further provides an explanation for why roots became significantly longer (16.15% increase) without a corresponding increase in fresh weight. The lettuce roots submerged in magnetically treated nutrient solution tended to prioritize elongation growth rather than biomass accumulation which can be an exploratory strategy to maximize nutrient uptake.

Table 2. Main effects of Number of Magnets (Factor A) and Nutrient Solution Exposure Interval (Factor B) on the yield performance of Lettuce using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test

Factors	Mean \pm SD	% Change	p-values [HSD (0.05)]		
			Factor	A x B	Block
Leaf Fresh Weight (g) Grand Mean = 42.29 \pm 7.40 CV = 4.16 %					
A1	37.78 \pm 5.39 ^b	-	0.0001		
A2	46.78 \pm 6.48 ^a	+23.76 %	[2.61]		
B1	48.47 \pm 6.76 ^a	-	0.0001	(0.6277)	0.0002
B2	41.27 \pm 5.55 ^b	-14.85 %	[3.94]		
B3	37.13 \pm 5.54 ^c	-23.38 %			
Total Fresh Weight (g) Grand Mean = 46.30 \pm 7.83 CV = 5.23 %					
A1	42.11 \pm 6.90 ^b	-	0.0001		
A2	50.49 \pm 6.58 ^a	+19.90 %	[3.60]		
B1	53.17 \pm 6.80 ^a	-	0.0001	(0.9814)	0.0007
B2	44.98 \pm 5.74 ^b	-15.40 %	[5.43]		
B3	40.75 \pm 5.82 ^c	-23.36 %			
Dry Weight (g) Grand Mean = 0.11 \pm 0.03 CV = 12.86 %					
A1	0.100 \pm 0.026 ^b	-	0.0088		
A2	0.120 \pm 0.026 ^a	+20.36 %	[0.020]		
B1	0.133 \pm 0.029 ^a	-	0.0008	(0.3446)	0.0070
B2	0.108 \pm 0.014 ^b	-18.49 %	[0.030]		
B3	0.089 \pm 0.020 ^b	-32.58 %			
Root Fresh Weight (g) Grand Mean = 4.26 \pm 0.58 CV = 11.10 %					
A1	3.76 \pm 0.51	-	(0.3450)		
A2	3.96 \pm 0.66	+5.32 %			
B1	4.05 \pm 0.77	-	(0.3384)	0.0112	
B2	3.92 \pm 0.48	-3.21 %	(0.2231)		
B3	3.60 \pm 0.46	-11.11 %			

Note: a) Means of the same superscript are statistically the same. b) Bold face indicates significance at $p < 0.05$; not significant values are shown in parentheses. c) % Change is calculated relative to the first treatment level within each factor.

Furthermore, exposing the nutrient solution to magnetic fields at longer intervals (every two days and every three days) resulted in a lower yield performance compared to daily exposure. For leaf fresh weight, decreases of 14.85% and 23.38% were observed, respectively; for total fresh weight, decreases of 15.40% and 23.36% were recorded, respectively; and for dry weight, decreases of 18.49% and 32.58% were measured for every-two-day and every-three-day intervals, respectively. Based on this result, it can be concluded that increasing the nutrient solution exposure interval between magnetization events results in a decrease in yield parameters. The declining pattern on yield as influenced by exposure interval mirrors its influence on growth parameters, which reinforces the generalization that biological benefits of magnetization diminishes when exposure interval is increased.

This finding provides important refinement to the assumption that magnetization effects persist for a period up to 24-48 hours⁽²¹⁾. Despite every-two-day exposure (48-hour interval), falling within the reported physical persistence window, significant yield reductions ranging from 14.85% to 18.49% compared to daily exposure are observed. This confirms that the biological benefits for plant productivity decay more rapidly than the physical changes in water properties which provides a distinction with important practical implications for system design and operation. This observation agrees with the claims of several studies regarding the importance of exposure frequency in maximizing magnetic field benefits⁽²⁴⁾.

The practical significance of these yield findings extends beyond percentage increases. The 30.54% improvement in leaf fresh weight under daily magnetic exposure compared to every-three-day interval translates to an 11.3 g increase in marketable product mass. When multiplied across thousands of plants in a commercial operation, this increase represents meaningful economic returns that could justify the additional energy costs associated with daily recirculation. Furthermore, the 20.36% increase in dry weight indicates that magnetic field exposure enhances not only fresh market yield but also overall biomass production and nutrient accumulation, with potential implications for nutritional quality.

3.3 Energy Consumption

The annual electrical energy consumption (kWh) for each exposure interval (Factor B) and for a single setup with and without magnets (Factor A) is presented in Table 3. The number of operating days per cycle was based on the actual number of days that the pumps operate for a 28-day period (A1 - Without Magnets) and 24-day period (A2 - With Magnets). For a 28-day cycle, pump turns on for 28 days, 14 days, and 10 days for intervals B1 (every day), B2 (every two days), and B3 (every three days), respectively. In contrast, for 24-day cycle, the pump operates for 24 days, 12 days, and 8 days for intervals B1 (every day), B2 (every two days), and B3 (every three days), respectively. The shorter production cycles observed with magnetic treatment (24 days vs. 28 days) reflect the accelerated growth rate of lettuce exposed to magnetically treated nutrient solutions, which consequently increases the total number of production cycles per year (14 cycles for A2 vs. 12 cycles for A1). This calculation accounts for 24 days (A2) and 28 days (A1) per year allocated to maintenance and operation.

A comparison of energy consumption across treatments reveals trade-offs between exposure frequency and production cycle duration. For daily exposure (B1) and every two days (B2), annual energy consumption was identical (42 kWh and 21 kWh, respectively) regardless of magnet use, as the reduction in cycle length offset the increased recirculation frequency. For B3 (every three days), energy consumption was lower with magnets (14 kWh) than without (15 kWh), representing a 6.67% decrease.

Table 3. Annual electrical energy consumption at different numbers of magnets (Factor A) and different intervals of exposure (Factor B)

Factors	A1 (No Magnet)	A2 (With Magnet)
B1 (Everyday)	42 kWh at 28 days/cycle	42 kWh at 24 days/cycle
B2 (Every other day)	21 kWh at 14 days/cycle	21 kWh at 12 days/cycle
B3 (Every after two days)	15 kWh at 10 days/cycle	14 kWh at 8 days/cycle

When considering exposure intervals, moving from B3 (every three days) to B1 (every day) resulted in a 200% increase in energy consumption for systems with magnets (from 14 kWh to 42 kWh) and a 180% increase for systems without magnets (from 15 kWh to 42 kWh). These substantial increases in energy use are accompanied by corresponding improvements in growth and yield parameters, as well as an increase in the number of production cycles for systems with magnets (14 vs. 12 cycles per year), suggesting that the additional energy expenditure may be justified by the enhanced productivity observed under daily exposure.

4 Conclusions

This study explored the growth and yield parameters of lettuce as influenced by the nutrient solution exposure interval to magnetic fields. Based on the results: growth and yield parameters such as plant height (+8.54%), number of leaves (+5.48%), root length (+16.15%), leaf area (+8.28%), leaf fresh weight (+23.76%), total fresh weight (+19.90%), and dry weight (+20.36%) were all significantly influenced by the two factors (Number of Magnets and Nutrient Solution Exposure Intervals). On the other hand, the yield parameter root fresh weight was not significantly influenced (+5.32%, $p > 0.05$). These findings demonstrate that exposure of nutrient solutions to a magnetic field, particularly at daily intervals, consistently enhances above ground biomass accumulation and root elongation, while root thickening requires a longer period to manifest.

The current study provides the first systematic investigation of how exposure interval (daily, every two days, every three days) affects plant response in a hydroponic system enhanced through MWT. Also, the study offers the tradeoff quantification between energy consumption and biological benefit, showing that daily exposure requires 200% more energy than every three-day exposure but yields 23.76% higher leaf fresh weight. Lastly, the study demonstrates that the biological benefits of magnetization decay more rapidly (requiring daily exposure) than the physical changes in water properties (which may persist 24-48 hours), refining the assumption of Surendran et al. ⁽²¹⁾.

Moreover, as a result of this study, it is recommended for commercial hydroponic lettuce production; to maximize yield and shorten production cycles from 28 to 24 days, the nutrient solution should be exposed daily to a magnetic field. Also, growers should weigh the 200% increase in energy consumption against the 23.76% yield gain and the additional two production cycles

per year (14 vs. 12 cycles) when deciding on exposure frequency. And for energy sensitive operations, every other day exposure may offer a compromise, providing moderate yield improvements with lower energy costs.

Furthermore, for future research prospects, an economic analysis of the net returns from daily vs. intermittent magnetic exposure at commercial scales, investigation of magnetic field strength optimization (number and arrangement of magnets) in combination with exposure intervals, evaluation of the effects of magnetically treated nutrient solution on nutritional quality parameters (e.g., vitamin, mineral, and antioxidant content) of hydroponic lettuce; and validation of the observed interval dependent responses in other hydroponic crops to establish generalizable guidelines are recommended

In conclusion, this study successfully achieved its objectives by demonstrating that increasing both magnetic field strength and exposure frequency significantly improves lettuce growth and yield, with daily exposure producing the best results. The modest increase in annual energy consumption (from 14 kWh to 42 kWh per setup for daily vs. every three-day exposure to magnets) is justified by the substantial gains in productivity and the increased number of production cycles, making the combined MWT hydroponic system a promising intervention for sustainable soilless cultivation.

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